

The following solvent systems were used: (S_1), FA ($10^{-5} M$, $10^{-3} M$, $0.1 M$, $0.5 M$, and $2.0 M$) in conductivity water; (S_2), pure DMSO; (S_3), DMSO/1.0 M aqueous FA (1:9, 3:7, 4:6, 1:1 and 7:3); (S_4), methanol/1.0 M aqueous FA (1:9, 3:7:1:1, 7:3 and 9:1); (S_5), acetone/1.0 M aqueous FA (1:9, 1:1, 9:1); (S_6), propanol/1.0 M aqueous FA (1:9 and 9:1); (S_7), methyl ethyl ketone/1.0 M aqueous FA (1:9); (S_8), dioxane/1.0 M aqueous FA (1:9 and 9:1); (S_9), DMSO/1.0 M FA in methanol (7:3, 1:1, 3:7) and (S_{10}), DMSO/1.0 M FA in butanol (7:3, 1:1, 3:7).

Procedure: The sample solution (1 or 2 drops) was loaded on plain SG or impregnated SG chromatoplates and the plates were developed by the ascending technique with a solvent ascent of 10 cm in all cases. The cations were detected with conventional reagents. The front limit (R_f) and the rear limit (R_r) of the spots were measured and the R_f values were calculated from these values.

Results and Discussion

With most of the solvent systems, impregnated SG layers were found more selective (strongly sorbing) for metal ions than plain or unimpregnated SG layers. On impregnated SG layers, all metal ions except Ni^{II} and Co^{II} ($R_f=0.7$) did not show any mobility over the concentration range 10^{-5} – $0.1 M$ of aqueous FA. The mobility of UO_2^{II} , Al^{III} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} increases on further increase in FA concentration (i.e. 0.5 or 2.0 M) giving R_f value about 0.85–0.9 in 2.0 M FA. However, all other metal ions (Zr^{IV} , Bi^{III} , Cd^{II} , Ti^{III} , Ag^I , Pb^{II} and Ti^{IV}) remained at the line of application at all FA concentrations (10^{-5} – $2.0 M$). Hg^{II} and Hg_2^{II} showed tailing ($R_L - R_T > 0.3$) at all concentrations of FA while they moved with the solvent front on plain SG layers. The mid R_f values, given in parenthesis, for Al^{III} (0.65), Fe^{III} (0.55) and Zn^{II} (0.42) in 0.5 M FA facilitate the separations of Zn^{II} , Al^{III} and Fe^{III} from all those metal ions which have lower and higher R_f values. The most appropriate FA concentration range for the separation of metal ions was 0.1–0.5 M. To understand the sorption process of cations in aqueous FA, ΔR_f (R_f in 0.5 M FA minus R_f in $10^{-5} M$ FA) was calculated for all metal ions and the average ΔR_f was obtained for different metal ions. A plot between average ΔR_f and the charge of the metal ion (not shown) shows that as the charge increases, the difference in the R_f values also increases till it reaches to maximum for a charge of +3. There is sudden fall in ΔR_f value with further increase in charge probably because of the insoluble salt formation.

The chromatographic behaviour of metal ions on impregnated SG layers with (S_2)–(S_{10}) systems may be summarised as follows. (i) The chromatoplates were more stable in solvent systems containing alcohols or ketones compared to DMSO and dioxane containing solvent systems. (ii) All the cations showed very little mobility and remained near the point of application in pure DMSO and

DMSO–1.0 M aqueous FA (9:1) solvent systems. (iii) Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Ni^{II} , Fe^{III} , Th^{IV} and Hg_2^{II} showed occasional tailing with few solvent systems. (iv) UO_2^{II} , Zn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , and Co^{II} , generally, showed an increase in R_f values with the increase in the concentration of FA (S_3 – S_6 and S_7 – S_{10}). The presence of higher proportion of FA in solvent systems yielded more compact spots. With S_6 (propanol–1.0 M aqueous FA, 1:9) all cations except Se^{IV} remained near the line of application and thus Se^{IV} which goes with the solvent front can be selectively separated. (v) The mid R_f values for VO^{II} ($R_f=0.4$ and 0.51) in methanol–1.0 M FA (3:7 and 1:9) respectively leads to its separation from the cations that have higher and lower R_f values. (vi) Cations such as Th^{IV} , Zr^{IV} , Ti^{IV} , Pb^{II} , Ag^I , Bi^{III} , W^{VI} and Tl^{II} gave very low R_f values in all solvent systems.

All the metal ions except Al^{III} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} showed almost identical behaviour (low R_f) in solvent systems containing 1.0 M FA in water or methanol or acetone and DMSO in 1:1 ratio. The higher R_f values for Al^{III} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} in DMSO–FA– H_2O system compared to DMSO–FA–alcohol (methanol or butanol) system may be attributed to the higher dielectric constant of the former solvent system. Some important separations realised on impregnated SG layers in various solvent systems have been summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SEPARATIONS ACHIEVED EXPERIMENTALLY IN VARIOUS SOLVENT SYSTEMS ON IMPREGNATED SG THIN LAYERS

Solvent system	Separations achieved (R_f)
DMSO–1.0 M aqueous FA	
7:3	UO_2^{II} (0.75)– Fe^{II} (0.18) or Al^{III} (0.15)
1:1	UO_2^{II} (0.70)– Th^{IV} (0.05) Cu^{II} (0.2)– Ni^{II} (0.85) or Co^{II} (0.89) Zn^{II} (0.37)– Ni^{II} (0.83) Al^{III} (0.52)– Se^{IV} (0.95)– Ti^{IV} (0.02)
3:7	UO_2^{II} (0.52)– Ti^{IV} (0.0) or Th^{IV} (0.05) Ti^{IV} (0.0)– Fe^{II} (0.90)– Al^{III} (0.4) Fe^{II} (0.90) from mixture containing Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Cu^{II} and Th^{IV}
$10^{-3} M$ aqueous FA	Ni^{II} or Co^{II} (0.85) from mixture containing Fe^{III} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and UO_2^{II} (0.05)
Methanol–1.0 M FA	
1:1	Se^{IV} (0.95)– UO_2^{II} (0.58)– Ti^{IV} (0.01) Se^{IV} (0.95)– Ti^{IV} (0.02)– Fe^{II} (0.67) Hg_2^{II} (0.67)– Pb^{II} (0.01)

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